

Elastic buckling and capacity of transversely stiffened plate

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ABSTRACT

The design of stiffened plates loaded by in-plane compressive stresses transverse to the stiffeners is treated only superficially in the Eurocodes and other design standards. More studies are needed on the elastic buckling behavior of stiffened plates under such loading, and on developing adequate design rules. Analytical solutions for the elastic buckling load of stiffened plates typically neglect the torsional stiffness of the stiffeners, which for plates with closed stiffeners may have great significance on the buckling resistance. This paper investigates a stiffened plate with trapezoidal stiffeners, used as compression flange to large beams in an offshore floor structure and designed with the stiffeners oriented perpendicularly to the compressive membrane stress. The elastic buckling modes and critical stresses of the transversely stiffened flange plate are studied, and different ways of modelling the stiffened plate. Present models for determining the buckling capacity of transversely stiffened panels are very conservative.

Keywords: Stiffened panel, buckling modes, critical elastic buckling stress, Eurocode

1 INTRODUCTION

Stiffened plates (panels) are used in applications requiring low self-weight and high strength. Examples of use are in box- and plate girders in bridges, marine structures, containers, hydropower dam gates, etc. Stiffeners on plates are usually directed parallel to the direction of the major axial compressive force in the plate, and the stiffeners contribute thus to carrying the axial force and increasing the stiffened plate's buckling resistance. The design methodology for such axially loaded plates is well established, applying existing solutions for the elastic buckling stress of the stiffened plate and determining capacity following provisions given in the various standards. Common design models cover plates of regular shape and with regular stiffener configurations, and stiffeners of open or closed cross-section shapes. The most common design concept for the buckling resistance of plane unstiffened plates is the effective width model of von Karman, which is incorporated in Eurocode 3 (1, 2) for steel structures. Eurocode 9 for aluminium structures (3) uses an effective thickness model instead to represent the weakening effect from plate buckling. The latter model might have some advantages in how the effective area in a cross-section is represented. The Reduced Stress Method (RSM) of Eurocode 3 (1993-1-5, Plated structural elements (2)) has the advantage that it can be applied to a much wider range of unstiffened and stiffened plate geometries. The disadvantage of the RSM method is that it is based on the buckling stress limit of the weakest plate element of a stiffened plate assembly, with no load shedding to the plate elements with lower slenderness. This may lead to a conservative capacity prediction compared to the effective width method.

Some plated structures may experience in-plane compressive axial load perpendicular to the stiffeners, either as a single load component or in combination with axial load along the stiffeners, transverse

bending loads, etc. For an uniaxially stiffened plate, the axial loading transverse to the stiffener direction must be carried by the plate alone. The effect of the stiffeners is here that they stiffen the plate against buckling (4), either by confining the plate buckling to the spans between the transverse stiffeners or by altering the buckling modes. Examples of structures where the axial force is directed perpendicular to the stiffeners are shown in *Fig. 1*. For a catamaran (*Fig. 1a*), the twin hulls are connected by multiple tunnel frames (beams) where the stiffened bottom plate of the tunnel acts as a flange to the tunnel beam. The resulting load action on the stiffened bottom plate is in-plane tension or compression transverse to the stiffener direction. In launching a steel girder bridge (*Fig. 1b*), the longitudinally stiffened beam webs are subjected to large support forces, with compressive in-plane stresses acting transversely to the stiffeners of the web. This design issue has been the topic of investigations by Mensinger et al. (5) and Pourostad and Kuhlmann (6).

Fig. 1. a) Examples of panels subjected to compressive in-plane force perpendicular to the stiffeners. a) Catamaran twin hull - tunnel frame; b) Launching of a bridge; c) Floor structure in offshore module.

The third example is from a floor structure of an aluminium offshore living quarter module (*Fig. 1c*). The floor was made with beams of inverted T-shaped cross-section, with a deck of extruded aluminium profiles that were welded together and welded to the beam webs. The design load was a vertically distributed loading on the floor deck that gave bending of the deck itself and bending of the floor beams, the latter causing significant in-plane compressive stresses in the stiffened deck plate (the beam flange), transverse to the stiffeners. An experimental investigation of this offshore floor structure is reported by Kleppe et al. (7).

The elastic buckling stress, σ_{cr} , is an essential parameter in the design calculations of any compressed slender element. The most accurate prediction for the buckling stress for a stiffened plate is obtained by numerical simulations, for instance by a shell element model in a FE program. However, numerical modelling may be time-consuming and analytical approaches may be preferable, at least in the early

design phase. Several analytical expressions exist for determining the buckling stress for stiffened plates loaded parallel to the stiffeners (i.e., longitudinally stiffened panels) in the literature. Both EN 1993-1-5 (2) (steel) and EN 1999-1-1 (3) (aluminium) provide buckling formulas. However, only the aluminium standard contains formulas that properly account for the torsional stiffness of closed-section stiffeners.

The existing solutions for determining the elastic buckling stress are much scarcer for plates with stiffeners oriented transversely to the axial load direction. Therefore, this paper presents a few methods and theories for the determination of the buckling stress for such cases. Various computer programs and analytical solutions from the literature have been applied for this. The offshore deck case of *Fig. 1c* is used as a case study. The paper also briefly discusses how the design resistance can be determined.

2 ANALYTICAL AND NUMERICAL PREDICTIONS OF ELASTIC BUCKLING LOAD

The stiffened deck of the offshore floor in *Fig. 1c* is very slender concerning the compressive in-plane loading transverse to the stiffeners. The elastic buckling of the deck involves both the buckling of the deck plating, by plate buckling between the stiffeners, and buckling forms with deflections of the stiffeners. Existing methods to determine the buckling stress (σ_{cr}) for such elements vary in if and how they consider the torsional stiffness of the stiffeners, and how stiffeners with two webs (as trapezoidal stiffeners) are discretized and where the stiffeners are assumed connected to the plate.

2.1 Analytical solutions for the elastic buckling stress

Only a few references deal with the elastic buckling of transversely stiffened plates. For the basic case with a four-edge simply supported plate with equidistant stiffeners (*Fig. 2*), Timoshenko and Gere (8) (and Troitsky and Hoppmann (9)) solved the critical stress by using an energy approach. The deflection surface of the buckled plate was described with a double Fourier series. Similar approaches were also applied by Budiansky and Seide (10) and Rønning (11).

Timoshenko's formula for the elastic buckling stress for plates (panels) with any number (i) of transverse stiffeners, assuming equal plate spans, is given in *Eq. (1)*, which refers to *Fig. 2*. The solution assumes that the stiffeners buckle in only one half-wave in the stiffener direction (y -direction in *Fig. 2*), while the stiffened plate may buckle in many waves along the x -direction (the load direction). The energy contribution from the twist of the stiffeners is neglected.

Fig. 2. Plate with equidistant stiffeners (8, 9)

The critical stress of the stiffened plate is (9):

$$\sigma_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2 D}{b^2 t} \cdot \frac{(m^2 + \beta^2)^2 + r\gamma\beta^3}{\beta^2 m^2} \quad \text{with } D = \frac{E \cdot t^3}{12(1-\nu^2)}, \quad \beta = \frac{a}{b}, \quad \text{and } \gamma = \frac{EI_i}{bD} \quad (1)$$

Parameter m is the number of buckling half-waves in the load direction (x-direction), and r is equal to the number of transverse stiffeners +1, i.e., equal to the number of subpanels along the stiffened plate. EI_i is the flexural stiffness of the stiffener. To derive the minimum value of the critical stress from Eq. (1), one must try several numbers of half-waves (m).

Smith (12, 13) investigated the elastic buckling of transversely stiffened fibreglass-reinforced plastic panels with trapezoidal stiffeners, as in ship hulls. The buckling problem was solved by applying a "folded-plate analysis", where the stiffened panel was divided into plate strips representing the subpanels of the deck plate and the walls of the stiffeners. The elastic buckling stress was determined from differential equations and work equations. The advantage of the approach is that it accounts for the torsional stiffness of the stiffeners.

Smith presented a set of diagrams for his "approximate evaluation of interframe buckling" in (12). The three interframe buckling modes considered are shown in Fig. 3a, reproduced from Smith (12). The buckling stress may be read from diagrams, as shown in Fig. 3b. Details of the derivations and the set of equations are reported in (13). Smith's Type 1 buckling is the local buckling of the deck plate between and inside the trapezoidal stiffeners. The Type 3 mode is buckling with stiffener bow deflection, like the buckling mode shown in Fig. 5a (Abaqus FE model).

Fig. 3. Buckling modes and diagram for the critical load by Smith (12). a) Buckling modes; b) Diagram example.

2.2 Numerical models to determine elastic buckling stress

To study the results of theoretical and numerical predictions for the critical stress of the transversely stiffened deck shown in Fig. 1c, a stiffened panel (sub-section of the deck) with five extrusions (Fig. 4a) was modelled in various ways. The panel geometry is shown in Fig. 4 and corresponds to the investigated deck of reference (7). The plate thickness is 4.0 mm, and the thickness of the flange and webs of the extrusions are 4.5 mm and 3.0 mm, respectively, as shown in Fig. 4b. The width of each extrusion is 280 mm, and the width of the plate part inside the closed trapezoidal stiffener is equal to the width of the plate part between the stiffeners, each $280 \text{ mm}/2=140 \text{ mm}$. The height of the extrusion is 90 mm. The length of the deck extrusions, 2645 mm (Fig. 4 a), corresponds to the distance between

the beam webs of the offshore floor structure. The stiffened deck was modelled with simple supports along the four exterior edges. A parametric study in (7) showed that a sub-model with five extrusions/stiffeners was sufficient to predict the buckling modes and critical stresses of the actual floor deck that contained many more extrusions.

Fig. 4. Geometry of the transversely stiffened panel for the buckling stress study. a) Panel geometry – five extrusions; b) Cross section of one extrusion; c) FE shell model in Abaqus.

The buckling stress may be determined by using analytical models for plates with multiple transverse stiffeners, such as the Timoshenko model in Fig. 2, or from a shell element model or other numerical tools. When modelling a plate with five trapezoidal stiffeners in a simplified way, each stiffener may be considered as a discrete beam-type stiffener located in the plate in line with the centroid of the stiffener. Alternatively, the stiffener may be considered as two individual open stiffeners, each composed of one stiffener web and half of the stiffener flange (L- or T-type stiffener), connected to the plate at the junction line between the stiffener web and the plate. These two approaches give a different number of stiffeners and subpanels and different lengths of the subpanels. To derive results that could be compared between the various methods, three different widths (70/140/210 mm) were used for the outermost plate strip at the two long edges of the panel (see Fig. 4a). The essential point was to model equally long plate spans between the stiffeners, either 280 mm (for the closed stiffener modelled as one unit, located in the plate in line with at the centroid of the stiffener) or 140 mm (for the stiffener modelled as two open stiffeners). As indicated in Fig. 4a, the panel dimension a was therefore modelled

with lengths of 1400 mm, 1540 mm, or 1680 mm in the various models; the only difference is the width of the plate strips outside the outermost stiffener at the long edges. Length is here the dimension along the load, i.e., transverse to the extrusions/stiffeners.

A shell model was established in the FE program Abaqus (14), as shown in *Fig. 4c*. The model had a length of $a=1400$ mm and a width of $b=2645$ mm. Four-node linear shell elements with an approximate size of 20 mm x 20 mm were used. Weld zones of 40 mm width were modelled between the extrusions, marked as red in *Fig. 4c*. All four edges were supported in the z-direction. The compressive loading was applied to the model by displacing one of the long edges in the x-direction and restraining the opposite edge. The elasticity module is 70 000 N/mm² for aluminium.

Examples of buckling modes obtained with the Abaqus shell model are shown in *Fig. 5*, where figures *5a* and *5b* show the panel upside-down to display the stiffeners more clearly. *Fig. 5a* shows the first eigenmode (lowest buckling load) and is a "global" type of buckling where each of the stiffeners deflects in a bow, with a pattern of up-and-down deflections between the support lines (the beam webs). *Fig. 5c* shows the lowest buckling eigenmode with buckling confined to the plate, i.e., with the stiffeners remaining practically straight (eigenmode 6 in Abaqus). The buckling modes between eigenmode 1 and eigenmode 6 are combinations of upward and downwards buckling of stiffeners, combined with stiffeners that remain straight.

Table 1 shows the chosen model variants, the determined buckling stresses, and the number of buckle half-waves along the x-axis of the panel. Results are shown for two shell element models in Abaqus, three models established in the freeware computer program EBPlate (15), and the analytical solutions from the literature (Timoshenko's and Smith's). The figures in the table show how the stiffeners were modelled in each case. EBPlate is a numerical program that calculates the in-plane elastic buckling stresses for unstiffened and stiffened rectangular plates. The plate's out-of-plane buckling shape is expressed with a Fourier series, and the Rayleigh-Ritz energy method is used to determine the buckling eigenmodes (16). EBPlate has two modelling options for stiffeners, where stiffeners are either treated as beams at discrete locations in the plate or the stiffeners are smeared out, and orthotropic plate theory is applied. EBPlate allows the modelling of trapezoidal stiffeners, but only with identical thicknesses for the sidewalls and stiffener flange. Therefore, an average thickness for the stiffener walls was determined such that the second moment of area of the modelled stiffener/plate in EBPlate became equal to that of the extrusion (*Fig. 4b*).

2.3 Results and comparisons of critical stresses

As shown in *Table 1* (first line), a regular Abaqus shell model comprising the five 280 mm wide extrusions has a model length of $a=1400$ mm and predicts a critical elastic buckling stress of 27.5 N/mm² for the panel. The panel buckles in five half-waves across the stiffeners (x-direction) and one half-wave along the stiffener direction (y-direction). The buckling mode is shown in full in *Fig. 5a*, displaying a pattern of alternating up- and down buckling of the five stiffeners (i.e., five half-waves along the loading direction).

The second line in *Table 1* is for a modified version of the Abaqus shell model, where a longitudinal slit is modelled in the middle of the flange plate of each stiffener, as shown in the inset figure in the table. The modelled flange slit divides the five closed stiffeners into ten open L-shaped stiffeners, each composed of one stiffener web and half of the stiffener flange. The plate is thus effectively supported by ten equally spaced stiffeners. The buckling stress of this model is 12.8 N/mm², with three buckling half-waves across the stiffeners and one wave along the stiffeners. The buckled shape of the panel for this version is shown in *Fig. 5b*. The modelled flange slit imposes a large reduction in the torsional stiffness of the stiffeners and eliminates the along-stiffener rotational rigidity provided

to the plate from the frame-type bending stiffness of the walls of the stiffeners. The reduction in the predicted buckling stress is more than 50% (comparing 12.8 to 27.5 N/mm²), which clearly shows the significance of considering the favourable effects of closed-section stiffeners in this case.

Table 1 Critical buckling stresses – panel with five trapezoidal stiffeners modelled in various ways.

FE-program or analytical method	Type of stiffener, number of the stiffeners and how they are modelled	Accounts for the torsional stiffness of stiffener	Length (a) of the modelled plate, number, and length of the subpanels	Critical stress σ_{cr} [N/mm ²]	Buckling shape/comment
Abaqus -shell model	Trapezoidal, 5 stiffeners 	Yes, as the closed stiffener	1400 mm, 2 · 70 mm + 9 · 140 mm	27.5	5 half-waves as shown in Fig. 5a
Abaqus -shell model with a slit in the stiffener flange	Trapezoidal, 5 stiffeners 	Yes, as the open stiffener	1400 mm, 2 · 70 mm + 9 · 140 mm	12.8	3 half-waves as shown in Fig. 5b
EBPlate -closed stiffeners	Trapezoidal, 5 stiffeners 	Yes, as the closed stiffener	1400 mm, 2 · 70 mm + 9 · 140 mm	21.5	5 half-waves
EBPlate -open stiffeners	T-shaped, 10 stiffeners, each as half of a trapezoid 	Yes, as the open stiffener	1540 mm, 11 · 140 mm	11.5	3 half-waves
EBPlate -orthotropic theory	Trapezoidal, 5 stiffeners smeared out 	No	1680 mm, 6 · 280 mm	10.7	4 half-waves
Timoshenko	Trapezoidal, 5 stiffeners	No	1680 mm, 6 · 280 mm	10.3	4 half-waves ($m = 4$)
Timoshenko	T-shaped, 10 stiffeners, each as half of a trapezoid	No	1540 mm, 11 · 140 mm	10.3	3 half-waves ($m = 3$)
Smith	Trapezoidal shape, no. of stiffeners is not a parameter	Yes	-	16.1	Solution independent of no. of stiffeners and buckles

Fig. 5. Buckling modes from Abaqus. a) Trapezoidal stiffeners, every second stiffener buckles up and down; b) Trapezoidal stiffener equipped with a slit, buckling occurs in 3 half-waves; c) Trapezoidal stiffeners, local buckling of the plate, but with the stiffeners remaining straight.

A model in the EBPlate program (inset figure in the third row of *Table 1*), applying the trapezoidal section option of the program for the stiffeners, yields a buckling stress of 21.5 N/mm^2 and a buckling shape with five half-waves across the stiffeners. EBPlate includes and determines internal work from the twist of the stiffeners from the out-of-plane displacements of the plate at the junction lines between the stiffener webs and the plate, flexural work from the transverse bending of the stiffener walls and torsional work from torsional rotation along the web-to-plate junction lines under certain assumptions (16). The difference from the comparable Abaqus result (first line in *Table 1*, stress 27.5 N/mm^2) is not large but still significant.

An EBPlate model with the five trapezoidal stiffeners modelled as ten open-section T-stiffeners (fourth row in *Table 1*) gives a spacing of 140 mm between the stiffeners. In this model, the plate panels outside the outermost stiffener at each edge were also modelled 140 mm long, which gives a model length $a=1540 \text{ mm}$ (eleven equally long subpanels in the model to allow comparison with *Eq. 1*). The EBPlate model predicts a buckling stress of 11.5 N/mm^2 and buckling with three half-waves across the stiffeners. This buckling stress is in very good agreement with the Abaqus result for the open (flange-slit) stiffener model which gave 12.8 N/mm^2 .

The third EBPlate model applies the smeared stiffener orthotropic stiffness option of the program, which requires a model length of $a=1680 \text{ mm}$ ($6 \cdot 280 \text{ mm}$ wide subpanels) because the number of stiffeners and their spacings are the only provided input options. EBPlate considers the axial and bending stiffnesses of smeared stiffeners by adding terms to the work equations for the plate but neglects the torsional stiffnesses (16). The critical buckling stress determined for this model is 10.7 N/mm^2 , with a buckling with four half-waves in the x-direction, thus exhibiting a slightly lower stress

than those determined by the two open-stiffener models (line 2 and line 4 of Table 1, respectively 12.8 and 11.5 N/mm²).

Predictions by the Timoshenko solution, *Eq. (1)*, are also given for two panel versions. With the five transverse stiffeners modelled as individual stiffeners, the solution requires a model length of $a=1680$ mm (six equally long subpanels of 280 mm). Correspondingly, with the stiffeners modelled as ten open stiffeners, the model length becomes $a=1540$ mm (eleven 140 mm long subpanels). The second moment of the area of the modelled stiffeners was determined for both models by assuming a contributing plate width of $10 t$ as the flange on each side of the webs of the stiffeners. The determined buckling stress is 10.3 N/mm² for both models, with four and three buckling half-waves across the stiffeners (*Table 1*). The equal buckling stresses between these quite different models are likely coincidental. If the contributing flange width was set to $15 t$ on each side of the stiffener webs, then the buckling stresses would become 10.9 and 11.2 N/mm², respectively. Compared to the buckling stress ($\sigma_{cr}=27.5$ N/mm²) predicted by the Abaqus shell model with closed trapezoidal stiffeners (first line in *Table 1*), the determined buckling stresses of the Timoshenko model are less than half. However, compared to the predictions of the Abaqus and EBPlate models with open stiffeners (buckling stresses of 12.8 and 11.5 N/mm², respectively), the agreement is very good. The slightly higher buckling stress predictions of Abaqus and EBPlate are likely because these models consider the relatively small torsional stiffness of the open stiffeners.

The last row in *Table 1* shows the critical stress predicted by the analytical buckling solutions by Smith (12, 13), illustrated in *Fig. 3*, where Type 3 becomes decisive. The predicted buckling stress is 16.1 N/mm², which is a significant improvement compared to the predictions of the open stiffener models in *Table 1* (ranging from 10.3 to 12.8 N/mm²). The decisive Type 3 buckling, by up-and-down buckling of the stiffeners, is identical to the lowest buckling mode predicted by the Abaqus model (first line in *Table 1*). However, the predicted stress of 16.1 N/mm² is considerably lower than the predictions by the Abaqus and EBPlate closed-stiffener models (27.5 N/mm² and 21.5 N/mm², respectively). The underprediction of the Smith model is likely due to the assumptions of the folded plate approach.

A lower bound estimate of the buckling stress of the panel may be determined by totally neglecting the stiffeners, i.e., to consider the panel as a uniform plate of length $a=1400$ mm and width $b=2645$ mm, which buckles in one large buckle. This simplification is suggested in EN 1999-1-1 (3) (as being conservative). With the plate's aspect ratio of $a/b=1400$ mm/2645 mm, the buckling coefficient is $k_{\sigma} = \left(\alpha + \frac{1}{\alpha}\right)^2 = 5.85$, which yields a classical buckling stress of approximately $\sigma_{cr} = 1$ N/mm², which is extremely conservative here.

On the other extreme, if the stiffeners of the panel were stiff enough to remain straight, the buckles in the axially compressed deck plate would be confined to the narrow regions between the stiffener webs, and the buckling pattern would become quite like that in *Fig. 5c*. Each sub-panel of the deck plate would then buckle like a continuous wide column over several equal spans of length 140 mm. The column buckling of this case is approximately $\sigma_{cr,column} = 50$ N/mm².

Adopting the lowest buckling stress ($\sigma_{cr}=27.5$ N/mm²) of the Abaqus shell model (*Fig. 5a*) as the "correct" buckling stress for the panel, i.e., buckling Mode 1 with the repeated up- and down buckling of the stiffeners, it is seen that the buckling stress of the two plate-models above (buckling of the unstiffened deck plate versus column behaviour of the sub-plates of the deck) enclose this stress. The range (1 N/mm² to 50 N/mm²) is of course too wide for the limits to be used as a design basis. Developing an accurate analytical model for the determination of the buckling stress of such panels remains a challenge.

3 PREDICTIONS OF ULTIMATE RESISTANCE

The Eurocodes do not state explicit design recommendations for the buckling capacity of transversely stiffened panels. However, some simplified methods may be suggested within the framework of the standards. The floor deck in *Fig. 4* (with five extrusions) is again used as an example. Remember that the critical elastic buckling stress of this panel determined by the Abaqus model was $\sigma_{cr}=27.5$ N/mm². The results are presented in *Table 2*.

The panel consists of extruded aluminium profiles in alloy EN-AW 6085 temper T6 with yield strength $f_o=250$ N/mm² (EN 1999-1-1), and with strength $f_{o,haz}=125$ N/mm² in the heat affected weld zone between the profiles (HAZ indicated in *Fig. 4c*). In clause 6.6.1(4) of EN 1999-1-1 (3), it is a suggested option to neglect the stiffeners when determining the transversely stiffened plate's resistance to axial compressive force. The plate (1400 mm by 2645 mm) is here extremely slender. A calculation according to the effective thickness method of EC9 yields a buckling stress resistance σ_{Rd} of 10.9 N/mm² (using partial factor 1.0). For the same aluminium plate, applying the effective width method of FprEN 1993-1-5 and the prescribed interaction between plate-like and column-like buckling, the buckling stress resistance becomes $\sigma_{Rd}=10.4$ N/mm² (*Table 2*). As expected, the two standards yield quite similar resistances.

A less conservative prediction may be obtained using the reduced stress method (RSM) of FprEN 1993-1-5 (17), which accounts for the beneficial buckling restraints provided by the stiffeners. The method requires the critical plate- and column buckling stresses to determine a *stress limit* (17). The buckling stresses may be determined by numerical analyses as Abaqus. Using the critical buckling stress $\sigma_{cr} = 27.5$ N/mm² (Abaqus) for the plate behaviour and the HAZ material strength of 125 N/mm² for the deck plate, the buckling stress resistance becomes $\sigma_{Rd}=22.5$ N/mm² (*Table 2*). If the input critical plate (and column) stress is based on the analytical solution by Smith ($\sigma_{cr}=16.1$ N/mm²), the RSM prediction becomes $\sigma_{Rd}= 13.9$ N/mm².

The highest resistance is achieved with a nonlinear FE capacity analysis in Abaqus, as seen in *Table 2* ($\sigma_{Rd}= 36.1$ N/mm²). This result was obtained by considering imperfections and nonlinear material behaviour, using different material properties in the elements outside and within the HAZ. The imperfections and residual stresses were included by using the equivalent imperfections prescribed by FprEN 1999-1-1 Annex B (18). These are a global bow imperfection of L/1000 for the extruded profiles/stiffeners and local imperfections (min(a/200, b/200) for the sub-plates between the stiffeners. The imperfection amplitudes applied in the simulations were 2.65 mm (stiffener bow) and 0.7 mm (plate imperfection), respectively. Following the prescribed procedure, these two imperfection patterns were imposed with a leading imperfection combined with a complementary imperfection reduced by a factor of 0.7 (18), each imperfection tested as the leading. The numerical loading was a uniform axial compression displacement applied in increments at one edge of the panel, restrained at the opposite edge (*Fig. 4c*). The ultimate stress determined in the Abaqus simulation was 36.1 N/mm², which is 1.6 times the resistance determined with the RSM, or more than three times the resistance of the plate without the stiffeners (*Table 2*). For comparison, also the version of the stiffened panel with a longitudinal slit in the five stiffeners was simulated (open stiffeners), giving a stress resistance of 27.3 N/mm². This suggests that the torsional stiffness of the stiffeners is important for the present case, and ought to be addressed also in analytical models.

Fig. 6 shows a plot of the deformed panel and the plastic strains at ultimate force. The deformation pattern has a large similarity with the elastic buckling mode (eigenmode 1, *Fig. 5a*). Yielding occurs first in the weld zone between the extrusions due to the reduced strength in the HAZ. The initially uniform distribution of the membrane stress (σ_x) in the deck plate is at the ultimate force changed to

a highly nonlinear distribution, with the stress lowered in the middle of the deck (due to the stiffener buckling deflections) and correspondingly increased at the supported longitudinal edges (the beam webs). The ratio between these stresses is approximately 1/10 at ultimate (7).

Table 2 Buckling resistance (capacity) – panel with five extrusions.

Method	Input critical stress σ_{cr} [N/mm ²]	Resistance σ_{Rd} [N/mm ²]
EC9, effective thickness method neglecting stiffeners	-	10.9
EC3, effective width method neglecting stiffeners	0.88	10.4
EC3, Reduced Stress Method, buckling stress σ_{cr} from Abaqus	27.5	22.5
EC3, Reduced Stress Method, buckling stress σ_{cr} from Smith	16.1	13.9
Abaqus nonlinear capacity analysis	-	36.1

Fig. 6. Equivalent plastic strains and displacements ($\times 7$) of the panel – at maximum force

4 SUMMARY

Analytical design methods for stiffened plates loaded with axial compression perpendicular to the stiffeners' direction are not well covered in the Eurocodes. The Reduces Stress Method deals with this loading but requires the critical elastic buckling stress of the stiffened plate, which often must be calculated by numerical tools. Especially for closed-section stiffeners with large torsional stiffness, numerical predictions are the only good alternative.

This paper investigated a sub-section of a stiffened offshore deck. It was found that analytical formulas for the elastic buckling of transversely stiffened plates predicted the buckling stress well if the panel was modelled with open stiffeners, giving buckling stress approximately 80% of the prediction of a shell element model in Abaqus. For the panel with closed stiffeners, the analytically determined buckling stresses were approximately 60% of the corresponding Abaqus prediction.

For the ultimate resistance of the panel with closed-section stiffeners, the most accurate prediction is obtained with the Reduced Stress Method (EC3), which gave a prediction of approximately 60% of the FE simulated resistance.

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